

Appendix 2. Examples of proposed primitive catalog for adapting web pages

Table 1. Examples of proposed primitive catalog for adapting web pages

id	name	adaptType	params	body	field
1	translatePageContent	Content	{targetLanguage}	let translationEngine = new pageTranslatorEngine(); translationEngine.execute(pageTranslator.detectLangWPPageAttributes(), targetLanguage);	IA_Language
2	changeFont	Presentation	{fontSize,measure}	let size = fontSize + measure; setStyle("*.accessibility-panel):not(accessibility-panel *)", {"font-size": size + " !important"});	IA_BaseFontSize
3	changeFontFamily	Presentation	{font}	tracker.set("*.not(i):not(span):not(.fa):not(.fas):not([class*='icon'])", {"font-family": font + " !important"});	IA_FontFamily
4	setPointerSize	Interaction	{size}	document.documentElement.classList.add("cursor-" + String(size).toLowerCase());	IA_MouseSize
5	highlightHyperlinks	Presentation	{}	document.documentElement.classList.add("highlight-element-a");	IA_HyperlinkColor
6	increaseInteractiveElementsOnHover	Interaction	{}	document.documentElement.classList.add("increase-interactive-elements-hover");	IA_HyperlinkDensity
7	applyHighContrast	Presentation	{}	document.documentElement.classList.add("high-contrast");	IA_PageColorContrast
8	createGuideLine	Interaction	{}	let guideLine = document.querySelector(".guide-line"); if (!guideLine) { guide = new guideManager(); guide.createGuideElements(); guideLine = document.querySelector(".guide-line"); } document.addEventListener("mousemove", (event) => { event.preventDefault(); guideLine.style.top = event.clientY + "px"; }); guideLine.classList.add("guide-line-active");	IA_RuleGuide
9	removeGuideLine	Interaction	{}	let guideLine = document.querySelector(".guide-line"); if (!guideLine) return; document.removeEventListener("mousemove", (event) => { event.preventDefault(); guideLine.style.top = event.clientY + "px"; }); guideLine.classList.remove("guide-line-active");	IA_RuleGuide
10	hideAnimations	Content	{}	document.documentElement.classList.add("hide-animations");	IA_PageContentAnimations

Table 2. Examples of proposed adaptation rules for older adult users for the InitialLoad event

Id	Name	Event	Condition	Action	Modified attribute	Auto executable	Translations	Priority
1	Auto translate the page	InitialLoad	UA_AutoTranslation == "true"	{translatePageContent(UA_LanguagePreference);}	"IA_Language"	false	{"en": {"description": "Translate webpage"}, "es": {"description": "Traducir página web "}}	1
2	Set Text size preference	InitialLoad	UA_FontSizePreference != null	{changeAttributeValue("IA_BaseFontSize", "UA_FontSizePreference")}	"IA_BaseFontSize"	true	{"en": {"description": "Modify text size"}, "es": {"description": "Modifica tamaño de la fuente"}}	1
3	Increase the size of the mouse cursor for motor limitation	InitialLoad	UA_MotorLimitation == "Medium" UA_MotorLimitation == "High"	{mousePointerSize("High");}	"IA_MouseSize"	false	{"en": {"description": "Change the cursor size"}, "es": {"description": "Incrementar el tamaño del cursor"}}	2
4	Highlight hyperlinks	InitialLoad	UA_HyperlinkRecognition == "Low"	{changeAttributeValue("IA_HyperlinkColor", "highlight-element-a")}	"IA_HyperlinkColor"	false	{"en": {"description": "Highlight the hyperlinks elements"}, "es": {"description": "Marcar los hipervínculos de la página web"}}	5
5	Increase size of the interactive elements for mouse skill	InitialLoad	UA_MotorLimitation == "High" && (UA_MouseSkill == "Low" UA_MouseSkill == "Medium")	{changeAttributeValue("IA_HyperlinkDensity", "increase-interactive-elements-hover")}	"IA_HyperlinkDensity"	false	{"en": {"description": "Increase the size of interactive elements when hovered"}, "es": {"description": "Incrementar el tamaño de los elementos interactivos al pasar el cursor por encima"}}	2
6	Apply high contrast	InitialLoad	IA_PageColorContrast <= 0.5 && (UA_VisionLimitation == "Medium" UA_VisionLimitation == "High")	{changeAttributeValue("IA_PageColorContrast", "high-contrast")}	"IA_PageColorContrast"	false	{"en": {"description": "Change the contrast color"}, "es": {"description": "Cambiar el contraste de colores"}}	5
7	Apply Reading Ruler	InitialLoad	(IA_PageTextDensity >= 0.7) && (UA_VisionLimitation == "High")	{createGuideLine();}	"IA_RuleGuide"	false	{"en": {"description": "Show guide line"}, "es": {"description": "Mostrar línea guía"}}	5
8	Change the font size for vision limitations	InitialLoad	IA_FontSizeReadability < 0.75 && (UA_VisionLimitation == "Medium" UA_VisionLimitation == "High")	{changeAttributeValue("IA_BaseFontSize", 16)}	"IA_BaseFontSize"	false	{"en": {"description": "Change the font size"}, "es": {"description": "Cambiar el tamaño de las letras"}}	5
9	Hide multimedia elements	InitialLoad	IA_PageTextDensity < 0.4 && UA_ConcentrationLevel == "Low"	{changeAttributeValue("IA_PageContentAnimations", "hide-animations")}	"IA_PageContentAnimations"	false	{"en": {"description": "Hide multimedia elements"}, "es": {"description": "Ocultar elementos multimedia"}}	5